

REMOTE MONITORING OF PATIENTS WITH COVID-19 VIRUS DISEASE, EBOLA VIRUS DISEASE AND LASSA FEVER USING WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS (WSNs)**¹Alumona Theophilus Leonard. ²Osakwe Anthony Nnamdi. ³Alagbu Ekenedilichukwu Emmanuel ⁴, Ezeonyi Nnaemeka Uchenna, ⁵Ogbodo Emmanuel Utochukwu**¹Electronic and Computer Engineering, NnamdiAzikiwe University Awka, Anambra State Nigeria²Huawei Technologies Company (Nigeria) LTD,³ Electronic and Computer Engineering, NnamdiAzikiwe University Awka, Anambra State Nigeria⁴Computer Science Department, NnamdiAzikiwe University Awka, Anambra State Nigeria⁵ Electronic and Computer Engineering, NnamdiAzikiwe University Awka, Anambra State Nigeria

Abstract

COVID-19 is a non-segmented, positive sense RNA virus., COVID-19 is part of the family of coronaviruses. This contains Four coronaviruses which are widely distributed and usually cause the common cold (but *can* cause viral pneumonia in patients with comorbidities). Corona virus can spread from an infected person's mouth or nose in small liquid particles when they cough, sneeze, speak, sing or breathe. These particles range from larger respiratory droplets to smaller aerosols. Someone can be infected by breathing in the virus if you are near someone who has COVID-19, or by touching a contaminated surface and then your eyes, nose or mouth. The virus spreads more easily indoors and in crowded settings It is normal for viruses to change and evolve as they spread between people over time. When these changes become significantly different from the original virus, they are known as "variants." To identify variants, scientists map the genetic material of viruses, A variant of interest becomes a variant of concern if it is known to spread more easily, cause more severe disease, escape the body's immune response, change clinical presentation, or decrease effectiveness of known tools – such as public health measures, diagnostics, treatments and vaccines. On the other hand Ebola virus disease (EVD) is a deadly disease with occasional outbreaks that occur mostly on the African continent. EVD most commonly affects people and nonhuman primates (such as monkeys, gorillas, and chimpanzees). It is caused by an infection with a group of viruses within the genus *Ebolavirus* Transmission of Lassa virus to humans occurs most commonly through ingestion or inhalation . Mastomys rodents shed the virus in urine and droppings and direct contact with these materials, through touching soiled objects, eating contaminated food, or exposure to open cuts or sores, can lead to infection, Monitoring and managing potential infected patients of COVID-19 , Ebola and Lassa Fever is still a great challenge for the latest technologies This paper x-rayed a networking solution in which Sensor (Medical Super Sensor - MSS) is used to collect multiple physiological signs sensed by each of the body sensors in wireless body area network and forwards them to the personal server and an Intelligent Personal Digital Assistant (IPDA) is used as a personal server; it has the ability to collect patient's vital signs and prioritizes the data transmission based on patient's current condition and data content remotely .

Keywords: Coronavirus, Ebola, Lassa Fever , Covid-19 Variant- alpha, Beta , Gamma, Omicron, Covid-19 Vaccines, Wireless sensor network (WSN),

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the last few decades pandemic diseases primarily from the zoonotic (animal to human) origin, has ravaged most regions of the world especially Africa and Asia. Some of the recorded outbreaks are: the Ebola virus of 2014 in West Africa [1], the Marburg virus of 1967 and 2012 in Germany and Uganda [2] respectively, the Lassa fever of 2018 in Nigeria [1], the SARS-CoV of 2002 and 2003 in Guangdong province, China [3-6], and the most recent Coronavirus (COVID-19) of 2019 in Wuhan China [7]. Marburg and Ebola viruses are of the *Filovirus* family and as such their symptoms might not be easily distinguished. They are believed to be of a zoonotic origin based on the nature of similar viruses, with fruit bats and *Rousettus* bat [2] being the most likely source. The bats carrying the virus can transmit it to other animals, such as primates, spreading it to the human

population. Human-to-human exposure and transmission are also possible via direct contact with infected blood and body fluids [1] such as saliva, tears, excretions, vomits, and blood [2].

Lassa fever is an illness caused by Lassa virus, a single-stranded RNA hemorrhagic fever virus from the family *Arenaviridae* [2] [8]. Lassa fever virus is of a zoonotic origin. It spreads to people through contact with household items, food, water, or air contaminated with the droppings or urine of infected multimammate rats (*Mastomys natalensis*). These rodents live throughout West Africa in homes, and they can shed this virus without being ill. People most often become infected by inhaling air contaminated with aerosols of rodent excretions, swallowing the virus in food or contaminated utensils, preparing and eating multimammate rats (meat of wild or non-domesticated animals, called bush meat or wild meat, is often prized as a delicacy), and contact with open wounds [2]. There are 100,000 to 300,000 cases of Lassa fever each year in the world. Lassa fever heavily impacts Sierra Leone and Liberia in particular, where it causes an estimated 5,000 deaths and about 10%-16% of admissions to hospitals each year. Deaths are especially common in children. Case fatality is 1% in general (compared to 70% in Ebola virus). Severe cases have a case fatality of 15% [2].

The recent Coronavirus (COVID-19 or SARS-CoV-2) is a member of the subfamily *Coronavirinae* in the family *Coronaviridae* and the order *Nidovirales* (International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses). This subfamily consists of four genera on the basis of their phylogenetic relationships and genomic structures they are: *Alphacoronavirus*, *Betacoronavirus*, *Gammacoronavirus* and *Deltacoronavirus* [9]. Phylogenetics analyses taken and genome structure shows that bats appear to be the reservoir of the COVID-19 virus [7]. Experiment shows that these Coronavirus HCoV-OC43 and HKU1 which are one of the seven human Coronaviruses are likely to have originated from rodents [10-11]. Domestic animals may have important roles as intermediate hosts that enable virus transmission from natural hosts to humans. In addition, domestic animals themselves can suffer disease caused by bat-borne or closely related Coronaviruses. COVID-19 is transmitted via droplets and fomites during close unprotected contact between an infector and infectee. In China, human-to-human transmission of the COVID-19 virus is largely occurring in families. Hence the virus spread out from homes to different communities, most children who have contracted the disease is as a result of household involvements [7]. The latest report shows that as of March 20th, 2020 87 countries and territories around the world have reported a total of 246,773 confirmed cases of the Coronavirus with a 10,062 deaths toll and 88,488 cases of recovery. Asia continent ranked the highest with China having 80,967 confirmed cases with 3,248 deaths toll. Below is death profile since the outbreak of the COVID-19.

Total Deaths of Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV/ COVID-19) [12].

DATE	TOTAL DEATH	CHANGE IN TOTAL	CHANGE IN TOTAL (%)
March 19	10,031	1,080	12%
March 18	8,951	973	12%
March 17	7,978	817	11%
March 16	7,161	642	10%
March 15	6,519	686	12%
March 14	5,833	404	7%
March 13	5,429	448	9%
March 12	4,981	353	8%
March 11	4,628	332	8%
March 10	4,296	271	7%
March 9	4,025	198	5%
March 8	3,827	228	6%
March 7	3,599	105	3%
March 6	3,494	107	3%
March 5	3,387	102	3%
March 4	3,285	83	3%
March 3	3,202	85	3%
March 2	3,117	67	2%
March 1	3,050	73	2%
February 29	2,977	54	2%

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February 28	2,923	65	2%
February 27	2,858	58	2%
February 26	2,800	37	1%
February 25	2,763	64	2%
February 24	2,699	81	3%
February 23	2,618	158	6%
February 22	2,460	100	4%
February 21	2,360	113	5%
February 20	2,247	121	6%
February 19	2,126	117	6%
February 18	2,009	136	7%
February 17	1,873	98	6%
February 16	1,775	106	6%
February 15	1,669	143	9%
February 14	1,526	143	10%
February 13	1,383	122	10%
February 12	1,261	146	13%
February 11	1,115	97	10%
February 10	1,018	108	12%
February 9	910	97	12%
February 8	813	89	12%
February 7	724	86	13%
February 6	638	73	13%
February 5	565	73	15%
February 4	492	66	15%
February 3	426	64	18%
February 2	362	58	19%
February 1	304	45	17%
January 31	259	46	22%
January 30	213	43	25%
January 29	170	38	29%
January 28	132	26	25%
January 27	106	26	33%
January 26	80	24	43%
January 25	56	15	37%
January 24	41	16	64%
January 23	25	8	47%

Viral Diseases, Incubation period, Sign and Symptoms [1][2][7]

S/N	VIRAL DISEASES	INCUBATION PERIOD	SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS
1.	Marburg Virus (Fig I) [23]	5 to 10 days	Fever, chills, headache, and muscle aches. About five days after the symptoms first occur, other symptoms may occur as follows: rash (at the chest, back and stomach), nausea, vomiting, chest pain, sore throat, abdominal pain and diarrhoea. On severe cases symptoms include: jaundice, pancreatic inflammation, severe weight loss, delirium, liver failure, and massive haemorrhaging with organs dysfunction. Other complications include: retinitis, orchitis, hepatitis, uveitis, encephalitis, transverse myelitis
2.	Ebola Virus (Fig I) [21]	2 to 21 days	Ebola shows the same symptoms as Marburg with additional kidney impairment.
3.	Lassa Fever (Fig II) [22]	6 to 21 days (3weeks)	Fever, malaise, general weakness, severe headache, sore throat, chest, abdominal and back pain, nausea, ringing ears, vomiting and diarrhoea, cough and respiratory distress may occur if illness involves fluid in the lungs. . Haemorrhage is not common in less serious disease, but the loss of fluid from blood vessels into tissue may occur; this causes facial swelling, reddened whites of the eyes, and fluid around the lungs and heart. In severe cases:encephalitis with confusion, tremors, seizures, and coma. Organ failure and shock are often end-stage events. Some bleeding from mucous membranes occurs in severe illness.
4.	Coronavirus (COVID-19) (Fig III) [20]	mean incubation period 5-6 days, range 1-14 days	fever(87.9%), dry cough (67.7%), fatigue (38.1%), sputum production (33.4%), shortness of breath(18.6%), sore throat (13.9%), headache (13.6%), myalgia or arthralgia (14.8%), chills (11.4%), nausea or vomiting (5.0%), nasal congestion (4.8%), diarrhoea (3.7%), and hemoptysis (0.9%), and conjunctival congestion (0.8%).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, we reviewed only related research work done on various deadly diseases with causative agents (virus, bacteria and fungi) in a tabular form

S/N	TECHNIQUE USED	TARGET VIRUS	FINDINGS/ RESULT	COMMENTS
1.	Neuro-fuzzy	Ebola Haemorrhagic Fever (EHF)[16]	Result revealed that about 9 clinical symptoms and 29 clinical signs and symptoms further classified into 5 Tiers were used	MATLAB and Fuzzy Logic tool box were used to simulate the entire process
2.	Computing system focused on Collective Intelligence Multi-Model Integration Platform (Bayes Cloud)	Ebola Virus Disease (EVD)[17]	Situation awareness is created using the integrated EVD BN model. The level risks inherent in the surrounding regions are predicted using the model.	Bayesian Network (BN) Script categorized on diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis was deployed for the analysis and Modelling
3.	Adaptive neurofuzzy methodology	Tuberculosis [18]	The system was able to categorize theseverity level as mild, moderate, severeand very severe.	The system was simulated using MATLAB 7.0
4.	Neuro-Fuzzy	Lassa Fever [19]	Neuro-fuzzy CBR framework efficiently diagnose a suspected case of Lassa feverbased on the observed symptoms. And other chronic medical conditions such as HIV/AIDS, Influenza, Ebola. With future modification on software prototyping and disease machine learning using suitable programming language.	Robust Neuro-fuzzy CBR framework, comprising of Case Based Reasoning (CBR), Neural Network (NN) and Fuzzy Logic (FL) was used in modelling the system
5.	AI-powered Smart Helmet System (Fig IV)	Coronavirus (COVID-19) [20]	System works in real time by effectively monitoring persons affected with the virus (COVID-19) within a range of 5m in any kind of environment, displaying basic information of the person (Fig V), while alerting security personnel	Temperature sensing (using Infra-red sensors), Facial recognition technology with and alarm system were used developing the real time system.

Fig IV. AI-powered smart Helmet [20]

Fig V. Temperature reading from Infra-red sensor with displayed personal information [20]

3. Using Artificial Intelligent (AI) Approach to detect Coronavirus

Doctors in China have been given a new powerful tool to help them quickly diagnose potential coronavirus sufferers. Called inferVISION, this AI-based software can quickly highlight potential problem cases in record time. A team of physicians in Wuhan, China, at the Zhongnan Hospital are using GPU-accelerated software to detect the visual signs of COVID-19. This AI-based software relies on NVIDIA GPUs for both training and inference and is alleviated the pressure on overworked staff to screen patients for the virus. The software is greatly helping medical staff to prioritize those who are likely to have contracted the virus.

The software has been developed by a Beijing-based startup called infer VISION. This company is a member of NVIDIA's AI incubator Inception[24]. The software had originally been developed for detecting signs of cancer in lung CTs. Additionally, the software's models were already set up for detecting pneumonia prior to the outbreak of coronavirus and only needed some fine-tuning to be adapted. The AI behind the software was trained using more than **2,000** CT images of some of the first confirmed coronavirus patients in China.

NVIDIA's AI-based software has some fantastic advantages over its human counterparts. Foremost among them is its speed.

More conventional methods can take a considerable amount of time, especially with the current enormous demand for this kind of screening. With the software in their arsenal, doctors are able to rapidly determine the best treatment options for patients suffering from the virus.

Thus far the new end-to-end system has been deployed to at least 34 hospitals in China. It has also been used the review well over **32,000** cases of COVID-19 infected patients. The software has been trained using hundreds of thousands of lung images collected by hospitals all across China. In addition to being used in China, inferVISION's software is currently in evaluation by clinics in Europe and the United States. "inferVISION is fully committed to support the medical professionals and stand with the patients in controlling the 2019-nCoV outbreak," [24].

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Figure Vi Source : InferVision Software

4. METHODOLOGY

The system architecture of the proposed remote monitoring of coronavirus, lassa fever, Ebola and other contagious diseases of interest. The wearable sensors for remote healthcare monitoring system is composed of four tiers as shown in Figure 7.0, The first tier 1. Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) it is attached to intended patients with any of the contagious disease under study ; 2) Personal Server (PPS) using IPDA; 3) Medical Server for Healthcare Monitoring (MSHM) and 4) The patient to be monitored and manage

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Figure 7: Remote monitoring of patient with covid -19, Ebola and lassa fever using WSN

Deploying wireless sensor networks on smart devices can aid in monitoring contagious diseases like covid -19 Virus disease, Lassa Fever, Ebola virus disease etc while maintaining a reasonable level of distance especially for health workers and personnel. Contrary to the traditional sensor networks that are carefully planned and worn by health care workers and security agents and also deployed in the predetermined areas, WSNs can be deployed in an ad-hoc manner which make them robust, fault tolerance, and increase in spatial coverage. They can greatly be used to monitor and track conditions of affected persons in both cities and rural areas using an intranet or internet thereby reducing the stress and strain of healthcare and security workers, eliminate medical errors, reduce workload, increase efficiency of medical staff, reduce long term cost of healthcare services, and improve the comfort of the patients [13] and their privacy. Also, these systems provide useful methods to remotely acquire and monitor the physiological, signals without the need of interruption of the patient's normal life, thus improving life quality [14]. Sensor nodes embedded with automatic temperature alarm and Google geo-location system can be strategically placed on the human body to create a cluster that is called wireless body area network (WBAN) that can be used to collect patient's vital signs [13], as well as precise location. It is worth noting that sensor nodes are being operated by batteries, their power consumption during transmission must be minimal for efficient and reliable data transmission between WBAN and personal server. Using sensor nodes with communication technologies such as mobile phones *i.e.* PDA, General Packet Radio Service (GPRS), 3G, and 4G and recently 5G networks, the sensor network can keep the affected individual unaware, while creating awareness to care givers, doctor and security personnel about the variation in health status of the patient in question suffering from any of the contagious disease . This paper proposes a networking solution in which Sensor (Medical Super Sensor - MSS) is used to collect multiple physiological signs sensed by each of the body sensors in WBAN and forwards them to the personal server and thus leveraging on [15]. An Intelligent Personal Digital Assistant (IPDA) is used as a personal server; it has the ability to collect patient's vital signs and prioritizes the data transmission based on patient's current condition and data content.

Currently, **there is no licensed vaccine for** Lassa fever, although numerous candidates are in the development pipeline. These include DNA, RNA, live attenuated, and multiple different viral-vectored vaccine approaches are available and also **There's no cure for Ebola**, though researchers are working on it. There are two drug treatments which have been approved for treating Ebola. Inmazeb is a mixture of three monoclonal antibodies (atoltivimab, maftivimab, and odesivimab-ebgn). Ansuvimab-zykl (Ebanga) is a monoclonal antibody given as an injection

The types of COVID-19 that have been labelled as variants of concern are:

- A. Beta** The COVID-19 variant that was first detected in South Africa
- B. Gamma** The COVID-19 variant that was first detected in Brazil
- C. Delta** The COVID-19 variant that was first detected in India
- D. Omicron** The COVID-19 variant that was first detected in South Africa

- 5. To protect yourself and others from COVID-19:
 - Keep a distance of at least 1 metre from others
 - Wear a well-fitted mask over your mouth and nose
 - Open windows
 - Cough or sneeze into a bent elbow or tissue
 - Clean your hands frequently
 - Get vaccinated as soon as it is your turn
- 6. List of Covid-19 vaccine

Eight vaccines have been approved for emergency or full use at least on stringent regulatory authority recognized by the world health organization (WHO). This vaccines are listed as follows

- 1. Pfizer-BioNtech
- 2. Oxford-AstraZeneca
- 3. Sinopharm BIBP
- 4. Moderna
- 5. Janssen
- 6. CoronaVac
- 7. Covaxin
- 8. Novavax and five others are under assessment by the WHO: sputnik V, Sinopharm WIBP, Convidecia, Sanofi-GSK and SCB-2019

7. CONCLUSION

As with all viruses, SARS-COV-2, the virus that causes COVID-19, Ebola and Lassa fever will continue to evolve as long as it continues to spread. The more that the virus spreads, the more pressure there is for the virus to change. So, the best way to prevent more variants from emerging is to stop the spread of the virus. Monitoring and managing potential infected patients of COVID-19, Ebola and Lassa Fever is still a great challenge for the latest technologies. In this work Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) based wearable monitoring device is designed to measure various vital signs related to COVID-19, Ebola and Lassa fever. Moreover, the system automatically alerts the concerned medical authorities about any violations of quarantine for potentially infected patients by monitoring their real time GPS data. The wireless body area network (WBAN) placed on the body is connected to edge node in Internet of things (IoT) cloud where the data is processed and analyzed to define the state of health condition of the disease in question either lassa fever, ebola disease or covid -19 patients. The design serves as an essential platform that defines the measured readings of COVID-19 symptoms, Ebola virus disease Symptoms and lassa fever symptoms for monitoring, management, and analysis. With this wearable monitoring WSN it can be used to track the health and recovery of a COVID-19 patient, Ebola virus disease patient and Lassa fever Disease Patient respectively

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